

Interchangeability of Kinematic and Gravitational Time Dilation

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Abstract

This manuscript hypothesizes that space-time curvature is generated by the finite speed of interactions and motions within a given mass. Observational data is presented to support the hypothesis. The implications are explored for a wide range of scales, from micro to cosmological. Unaccounted-for relativistic effects might be responsible for what is perceived as dark matter, dark energy and great attractor.

A proposed validation of the hypothesis may bring a practical benefit. It may be possible to build an Alcubierre drive from an ammonia molecule. The frequent and spontaneous tunneling of the heavy nitrogen atom may create significant asymmetric space-time curvature that also allows electrical steering because the molecule is polar.

1 Introduction

Significant discrepancies exist between the theory and observations, which are being explained with dark matter and dark energy. Another invisible entity, the Great Attractor, is needed to explain the observations within our Laniakea Supercluster. There are also unexplained variations in the Hubble constant. Can these problems be linked to something more fundamental, such as the fact that we still do not understand why mass deforms space-time? The discrepancies may be due to predictions based on an incomplete theory. The challenges may come from the changing perspective of being an external relative to the gravitational mass observer in the Solar system to an observer witnessing gravity from deep inside the mass at the galactic and cosmological scale. Time dilation is relative and depends on the perspective. Therefore, it may be worth perceiving mass differently.

Any object maintains shape and volume due to the motions and interactions of its constituents. A galaxy would not be able to keep its shape and volume unless stars, gas and dust rotate around the galactic center. A planet would keep its shape and volume only because of the numerous electromagnetic interactions and motions within the sizeable gravitational mass.

To make it more intuitive, instead of shape and volume, we could think about the allocated space the mass takes. The next step would be to show that every mass lags relativistically to take its classically allocated space due to the finite speed of electromagnetic interactions. Then, the question would be whether this relativistic lag equals the gravitational time dilation.

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It may also be more intuitive to replace abstract time dilation with ease of movement. Instead of thinking of time slowing at the planet's surface, we could reason that it is easier for an object to move in that region. Consider the following analogy: It is hard to move near a water cannon, but it is easier to move far from the source, where the water jet slows down. Similarly, the relativistic lag of the mass to maintain its allocated space would produce the ease of motion (time dilation) similar to being farther from the water cannon.

The following sections present examples of the above logic applied at different scales.

2 Planetary Scale and P-wave Dilation

This section intends to show that a planet lags relativistically to keep its allocated space due to the finite speed of the electromagnetic interactions within the planet. To prove it, the average speed of the seismic pressure wave is compared to the escape velocity of our planet. A link between the kinematic time dilation of the P-wave and the gravitational time dilation is hypothesized.

In everyday life, we comprehend our planet as being rigid. However, continents drift, the core rotates, atoms vibrate, the electrons have angular momentum, etc. Numerous interactions are involved in maintaining the planet's shape and volume while it orbits the Sun.

We also usually think that the planet moves under its inertia, including all the particles it is composed of. However, the particles are not free to move, and they certainly do not move along straight trajectories. The particles vibrate, rotate, and interact. For the center of the planet to move, the outer layers must also move because they are interconnected with chains of electromagnetic interactions. On a smaller scale, when a soccer player kicks a ball, it takes time for the opposite side of the ball to move because the pressure wave must propagate through the ball. The electromagnetic interactions have finite speed. A relativistic lag may be expected to build up significantly over greater distances.

The gravitational time dilation is equivalent to a kinematic time dilation caused by the planet's escape velocity v_e according to the Schwarzschild metric.

$$t_0 = t_f \sqrt{1 - \frac{v_e^2}{c^2}} \quad (1)$$

where t_0 is the proper time between two events for an observer close to a massive sphere and t_f is the coordinate time between the events for an observer at an arbitrarily large distance from the massive object. Note, however, that the escape velocity in formula (1) expressed in density terms is roughly proportional to the number of particles interacting in the radial direction:

$$v_e = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{R}} \sim \sqrt{\rho R} \quad (2)$$

where G is the gravitational constant, and M and R are the Earth's mass and radius, respectively. Consecutively, (1) and (2) can be interpreted that the gravitational time dilation also depends on the number of interactions in the radial direction.

On the other hand, following the football analogy, we could consider the speed of a pressure wave since the speed of the seismic P-waves has been measured. It passes through the center of the Earth in 16-20 minutes. Based on the diameter, the average speed is 11.8 km/s ($= 12,742 \text{ km}/18/60$), which is reasonably close to the escape velocity of 11.2 km/s . Another supporting example can be the speed of the radial sound waves inside the Sun. It is estimated to be hundreds of kilometers per second along 90% of Sun's radius [1], while Sun's escape velocity is 615 km/s .

The formula for the P-wave speed is:

$$v_p = \sqrt{\frac{B}{\rho}} \quad (3)$$

where B is the elastic P-wave modulus, and ρ is density [2]. B is defined as the ratio of axial stress to axial strain in a uniaxial strain state. This occurs when expansion in the transverse direction is prevented by the inertia of neighboring material, such as in an earthquake or underwater seismic blast. When comparing v_p to the escape velocity, the average elasticity modulus B for a gravitational mass would be:

$$B = \frac{8}{3} \pi G \rho^2 R^2 \quad (4)$$

This formula would not hold for a small mass, where B does not depend on radius and density. However, formula (4) may apply to spherical mass that is shaped by gravity.

What are the implications?

Suppose space-time curvature is due to the finite speed of interactions within a given mass. In that case, the hypothesis implies that elementary particles do not generate gravity due to a lack of internal interactions that would produce time dilation. Therefore, applying the GR mathematical apparatus at the particle level is as meaningless as applying Pascal's pressure formula to a single molecule. Space-time curvature is continuous because the cumulative time dilation due to an enormous amount of quantum interactions smoothens out the quantization at the macro level.

According to this reasoning, quantized nuclear and electromagnetic reaction forces balance the gravitational attraction based on continuous space-time curvature. Gravity would be free to push the particles into prohibited quantum states, and the only escape route for the particles may be via quantum tunneling. The acoustic waves and the tunneling events may be powering stellar winds with speeds also in the range of v_p and v_e ($400 \text{ km/s} - 750 \text{ km/s}$ for the Solar wind). Then, every sufficiently large gravitational mass should produce stellar winds.

Formula (4) can validate the hypothesis by measuring the average P-wave speed passing through the Moon's or Mars's center, for example. Then v_p can be compared to v_e .

3 Galactic Scale and Rotational Dilation

This section intends to show that a galaxy partially lags to keep its allocated space due to the relativistic time dilation of the galactic rotation. A correlation between the total time dilation (kinematic + gravitational) and the rotational curves is presented. The gravitational time dilation is compared to the kinematic time dilation along the galactic radius.

According to the theory of relativity, there are relativistic delays caused by gravitational mass and relativistic motion [3]. This section follows the perspective of an observer located at the center of a galaxy, assuming it is not occupied by a stellar object. The same applies to an observer outside the galactic gravity well looking towards the rotating galaxy. In both cases, the observer is at a location with zero gravitational time dilation.

Figure 1 shows the gravitational time dilation ratio $GTD(r)$ computed based on the Schwarzschild metric:

$$GTD(r) = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM(r)}{rc^2}} \quad (5)$$

where r is the distance to the galactic center, G is the gravitational constant, and c is the speed of light. $M(r)$ is the mass (in solar mass units) residing in a sphere with radius r

$$M(r) = 2\pi \int_0^r R S_b(R) dR \quad (6)$$

where $S_b(R)$ is the surface brightness in units of the solar luminosity normalized by surface area, and r-band corrected for inclination and dust extinction [4,5].

The velocity time dilation ratio $VTD(r)$ is computed based on the special relativity formula:

$$VTD(r) = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2(r)}{c^2}} \quad (7)$$

where $v(r)$ is the rotational velocity measured at a distance r from the galactic center [4,5]. The data used to compute time dilation was summarized in an atlas [6] and available for download at the University of Tokyo website.

The total (combined) time dilation $TTD(r)$ is computed similarly to the way used for the Global Positioning System (GPS) corrections [7]:

$$TTD(r) = \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM(r)}{rc^2} - \frac{v^2(r)}{c^2}} \quad (8)$$

Figure 1 compares the computed time dilation based on measured velocities and optical photometry in the r-band [4,5]. The results show good agreement for mass derived from optical photometry in the r-band, denoted as ‘‘C-sample’’ [8]. The rotational dilation dominates the gravitational one far from the

galactic center. Thus, the deviation from the Newtonian model is not due to dark matter but to an unaccounted kinematic dilation component.

Figure 1. Correlation between combined time dilation and measured rotational velocities for # U111.

Similar correlations for other galaxies are also available [9].

Note that formula (5) may not be the most accurate estimate for the gravitational time dilation of a non-spherical object such as a spiral galaxy, so the correlation in Figure 1 may be further improved.

4 Intergalactic Scale and Rotational Dilation

This section intends to show that the rotational time dilation may be responsible for an essential portion of the space-time curvature in our and other galactic clusters.

4.1 The Great Attractor

The space-time curvature at the Solar System location within the Milky Way can be decomposed into gravitational time dilation component (equivalent to 550 km/s escape velocity) and kinematic rotational velocity term of 230 km/s ; see Figure 2. The vector sum produces 600 km/s , which is also the estimated velocity of the Milky Way towards the hypothetical Great Attractor.

According to the proposed model, the 600 km/s is not an actual velocity but a skewed perspective due to distorted curvature at our off-center location within the galaxy. The vector sum in Figure 2 also shows why the Great Attractor appears approximately in the galactic bulge direction.

Our 600 km/s -equivalent time dilation would also produce a bias in the redshifts of the galaxies in the local group creating a false motion appearance. The Earth would have created a similar illusion if it were transparent and allowed see-through observations through its center.

Figure 2. The Great Attractor may be illusionary due to the total time dilation at our location within the Milky Way.

4.2 ‘Ensemble’-Type Cluster

Figure 3 correlates the total time dilation with the rotational velocities in an ‘ensemble’-type cluster, which was built from the combined data from 59 clusters [10].

As expected, the kinematic time dilation component dominates the gravitational dilation for the entire radial range. In this case, the time-space curvature based on the Newtonian gravity term is insignificant compared to the kinematic dilation.

5 Cosmologic Scale and Gravitational Redshift

This section intends to show that the cosmologic redshift is gravitational. In other words, the redshift is how the universal gravity is perceived when observing the mass from the inside out. Which is an unusual perspective, since we have used to witness gravity as external observers of the mass concentrated in the Sun, Earth, and other members of the Solar System. It also means that the relative distances between the galaxies are not increasing due to expansion. Which may help with the latest discrepancies between the JWST data and the early galactic formation theory because the Big Bang starting point becomes unnecessary.

The universal mass that surrounds us lags to take its allocated space due to the cumulative (from our perspective) gravitational time dilation of its constituents. What is the total lag in this case?

Figure 3. Correlation between combined time dilation (8) and measured rotational velocities in a galaxy cluster.

The gravitational time dilation can be estimated from the escape velocity using the formula (1). However, this formula is based on time dilation perceived from an external to the mass observer. The dilation is caused by the energy loss of the climbing up the gravitational well photons and is proportional to v_e^2 for $v_e \ll c$. Mathematically, it is equivalent to a transverse Doppler effect.

Formula (2) can be rewritten in terms of density:

$$v_e \sim \sqrt{\rho R} \tag{9}$$

Figure 4 shows the perspective of an observer located at the center of a spherical volume with constant density ρ . Here, the time dilation should increase with the distance from the center R , and should be proportional to v_e for $v_e \ll c$. Mathematically, it is equivalent to a longitudinal Doppler effect since the velocity is not squared. From the observer's standpoint, the mass outside the sphere does not contribute to the space-time curvature because its gravity cancels out.

Why does the gravitational time dilation differ for an external and internal for the mass observer? The external observer witnesses energy loss, while the internal observer witnesses the relativistic delay of the quantum interactions within the mass. Internally, it is equivalent to the longitudinal Doppler effect caused by the radial P-wave, discussed in Section 2.

Photons redshift when moving from a region with higher to a region with lower time dilation. From our perspective, the time dilation is relatively lower at our location than at the periphery of any universal mega sphere surrounding us. Formula (9) resembles Hubble's law, with the exception that the Hubble constant would be proportional to $\sqrt{\rho}$ in this case:

$$H_0 = \sqrt{8/3\pi G\rho} \quad (10)$$

Another difference between formulas (1) and (9) is that high cosmological redshifts would not correspond to superluminal velocities according to formula (1). The reason for the recently measured H_0 variation may be that the H_0 value would drop because of the steep nonlinearity of formula (1) at the distances where the escape velocity is approaching the speed of light. CMB may also arise at distances where v_e is approaching the speed of light – a phenomenon resembling Hawking's thermal radiation near the event horizon of a black hole. In other words, the Hubble linearization (1) seems to be a non-relativistic approximation that is not valid for very large distances.

Figure 4. Dark energy or gravitational time dilation?

If the cosmologic redshift is gravitational, then the universal expansion would appear to be accelerating in the following way:

$$a = \frac{H_0^2}{2} r \quad (11)$$

where a is equivalent to the gravitational acceleration of a universal mega sphere with radius r . Correlations (10-11) may help to validate the hypothesis further.

6 Micro-Scale and Quantum Propulsion

The ammonia molecule NH_3 is known to invert its shape (Figure 5) billion times a second due to the spontaneous quantum tunneling of the nitrogen atom. The well-known phenomenon was used in the first atomic clocks and masers. This section intends to validate the main hypothesis by proposing a practical quantum propulsion method (Q-Drive) based on the presented interchangeability between kinematic and gravitational time dilation.

The heavy nitrogen changes its position with speeds near the speed of light. The resulting kinematic time dilation is asymmetric from hydrogen's perspective. The lagging shape change of the molecule should create significant local space-time curvature according to the logic described in the sections above. The three hydrogen atoms must respond to the relativistic changes in the molecule shape. The curvature asymmetry resembles the asymmetry required in the Alcubierre drive concept.

Figure 5. Nitrogen inversion.

The ammonia molecules are polar and can be oriented with an external electric field. The objective is to keep the tunneling events (and the asymmetry of the space-time curvature) unidirectional. Electric steering would be especially easy when the molecule's vibrational and rotational kinetic energy is insignificant at the low temperatures of outer space. The proposed experiment monitors whether the ammonia molecules accelerate translationally when exposed to a high-voltage field.

To create a macro effect, the tunneling events must contribute to the momentum transfer during the molecular collisions. Microwave energy may need to be pumped into the ammonia gas to excite the molecules. The excitation would increase the likelihood of the nitrogen inversion process contributing to the momentum transfer during molecular collisions. The excitation may also be improved by mixing the ammonia with helium. Then, the pressure bias on the container walls and resultant propulsion forces should be measured. Preliminary experiments suggest that slow motion of a 1-kg container may be produced even at room temperature using the above Q-Drive approach [11].

Note that the Q-drive is not based on chemical or nuclear reactions. Ammonia is not used as fuel but as a working fluid similar to the ammonia refrigerators, which makes the Q-drive environmentally safe.

It would also work anywhere since nitrogen inversion is always present, in space and at room temperature. However, the most significant benefit is that the Q-Drive seems to be propellant-less, which may enable interstellar travel.

7 Conclusions

Is space-time curvature created by the finite speed of interactions and motions within a given mass? Can gravitational and kinematic time dilation be interchangeable mathematically and observationally? Or could the presented several correlations be incidental?

The presented mathematical relations can produce predictions to generate additional observational correlations to validate or discard the hypothesis.

A successful development of a quantum drive would represent the ultimate validation and significant practical benefits, which would be impossible based on the existing theory.

8 References

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